

DISORDERS OF SENSORY FUNCTIONS.

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Abstract: According to the science of world psychology, perception is considered as a simple mental cognitive process consisting of reflecting some features of things and events of the existing world, as well as the internal states of the human body through the direct influence of material stimuli on certain receptors - this is the first stage of cognition

Key words: afferent, extero-receptive sense, interoceptive sense; proprioceptive sensations, intuition, perception, imagination.

Sensation is a reflection of simple images, symbols as some structural properties as a result of the impact on the senses, regardless of their micro- or macrostructure. A person learns the form of substances in the environment, the type of movements, their properties and specific features with the help of the senses.

According to scientific teachings about feelings, things and their properties, components, properties, forms and actions are considered primary, and the feelings themselves are influenced by external and internal stimuli on the sense organs. According to the information, the senses perceive the true image of material existence, reality, and therefore reflect the appearance, shape and characteristics of the material world as they are, without changes.

In psychology, the physiological basis and mechanisms of sensations are formed by the nervous process, its system, structure, which arises as a result of the influence of analyzers that are absolutely suitable for the stimulus itself. According to the teachings of physiologists and psychologists, the analyzer consists of three components that are in harmonious relationship with each other. Simply put, this content is arranged in the following sequence:

- 1) from the peripheral part, which converts external force into a nerve process, i.e. from the receptor;
- 2) from afferent (nerve fibers tending to the center) conductive nerves connecting the peripheral part of the analyzers with the central part;
- 3) nerve impulses coming from peripheral parts are processed by analyzers of the cerebral cortex.

In other words, peripheral nerve endings (such as eyes, ears, skin, nose), afferent and efferent nerve fibers form the spinal analyzer and brain analyzer centers.

According to the latest achievements and scientific terms of world psychology, sensations are classified as follows (the first appearance of this classification belongs to the English scientist C. Sherrington) :

- 1) sensory organs adapted to reflect the characteristics of things and events in the external environment and receptors located on the external part of the body, i.e. extero-receptive sensory organs (receptors);
- 2) sensations that perceive the state of the internal organs and whose receptors are located in the internal organs and tissues, i.e. interoceptive sensations;
- 3) sensations located in the muscles, ligaments, muscles, giving information about the position and movements of our body and body, i.e. proprioceptive sensations.

The first category includes such types as vision, hearing, smell, skin sense, and taste. Vision is a process of electromagnetic radiation in the range of 380 to 770 millimicrons. Hearing consists of sound waves with a vibration frequency of 16 to 20,000. The visual senses are located in the posterior part of the cerebral cortex. The sense of hearing is located in the superior gyrus of the cerebral cortex. Skin sensitivity and sensations of movement are located in the posterior part of the central fold of the cerebral cortex.

Now let's think about the description, essence and basis of feelings.

A. R. Luria , interoceptive sensations are not sensations in the original sense, but act as intermediate sensations between emotions and sensations. In psychology, the subjective appearance of these sensations has not been studied deeply enough, so they are included in the circle of "unknown sensations." An important role is played by familiarization with knowledge about them, checking for changes, and the "internal landscape of diseases."

in expression. They say that these conditions that arise from diseases of internal organs are of particular importance in the diagnosis of internal diseases (from the studies of A. R. Luria) .

Involuntary feelings of this nature awaken in a person very early, and their expression also has its own forms. For example, they manifest themselves as "premonitions", and even a person is not able to describe them; often these experiences appear in a dream and indicate an attack of some disease.

They manifest themselves in changes in a person's mood and emotional reactions, which causes a sharp change in the child's behavior. Because a child

does not have the ability to understand, perceive and feel changes in the internal state of parts of his body, so this can be felt by a general change in his behavior. An example of such a phenomenon is the following reality: a child begins to care for a “sick” doll in order to demonstrate his internal interoceptive feelings.

The objective significance of interoceptive sensations is very great, since they are the basis for ensuring the balance of internal processes. In other words, they are called hemostasis (stability) of metabolic processes in the body. Signals arising from within lead to the elimination and reduction of behavior, stress, tension and affective states, and the satisfaction of emerging tendencies. As a result, the functioning of the body's internal organs can get out of control. For this reason, interoceptive senses also play an important role in medical psychology. Somatic and visceral processes allow us to study the relationship between mental states.

The physiological mechanisms of interoceptive sensations, together with interoception, were studied in detail by K.M. Bikov , V.N. Chernigovsky . All this is interpreted based on the mechanisms of conditioned reflex activity.

Proprioceptive sensations provide signals about the spatial position of the motor apparatus and body. They form the regulatory and afferent basis of human movements.

Peripheral receptors are located in muscles, tendons and joints and have a special body shape. These cells are called Puccini cells .

Irritants arising in the body as a result of muscle tension and changes in the position of joints are transmitted to the white fluid of the posterior column of the spinal cord using nerve fibers. The stimuli reach the lower parts of the Burdak and Gaille nuclei and, passing through the subcortical nodes, complete their movement in the darkened zone of the cerebral hemisphere.

A. Orbeli, P.K. Anokhin (in animals), N.A. Bernstein (in humans) studied that proprioceptors are the afferent basis of movement.

According to psychological data, the sensitivity of body position in space is expressed in static lines. Its center is located in the internal auditory canals and is adjacent to each other in a space perpendicular to each other. For example, changing the position of the head is carried out according to the following scheme:

- a) the change is caused by endolymphatic fluid;
- b) auditory nerve;
- d) vestibular nerve;
- e) temporal cortex;

e) enters the brain apparatus.

The vestibular sensory apparatus is in direct contact with vision and is involved in the process of spatial orientation. For example, when a car crosses a road, when it crosses a dense forest, etc. The same can happen in flight. The same process occurs in the case of pathology.

Extrareceptive sensations are divided into nonspecific intermodal sensory groups, with the exception of modality (5). For example, you can feel 10-15 vibrations per second with the organ of hearing, but not with the ear, but with the help of bones (through the meninges, elbows, knees) - this is called vibration sensitivity. For example, the perception of sounds by deaf people holding a piano, the movement of the floor or furniture. Typically, vibration sensitivity is also called intermodal sensitivity. Another example of intermodal transport looks like this:

a) in the organs of smell, taste and taste;

b) with extremely strong sound, with extreme lighting;

y) tricheminal , i.e. a combined, integrative state of three different effects, etc.

A unique form of perception is cutaneous photosensitivity , that is, it is realized by distinguishing subtle shades of colors and feeling with the tips of the hands. Photosensitivity of the skin was discovered by A. N. Leontiev, which allows a rational approach to many cases. This discovery saw the face of the world, sending green and red light to the tip of the hand. By comparatively considering the connection of color signals with pain triggers, it is possible to teach a person to distinguish the colors that fall on the skin of the tip of his hand during active aiming.

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